

Research data infrastructure and services: Persistent identifiers for dataset elements.

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The presentation discusses current data citation hurdles in the Social Sciences and introduces the Persistent Identifier (PID) service for dataset elements as a technical solution, resulting from the consortium KonsortSWD (<https://www.konsortswd.de/>) of the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) (<https://www.nfdi.de/>). In the Social Sciences PIDs are only available on the study or dataset level, but not on the level of the inline data objects, such as survey variables. This is insufficient for unambiguous identification and ensures accurate data citation since researchers usually use only a subset of the elements in a dataset. Consequently, data citation practices vary widely (see <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7555266>), and researchers often do not follow a standard such as Data Citation Principles (Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles, see <https://doi.org/10.25490/A97F-EGYK>), resulting in inconsistent data referencing, provide insufficient metadata and incomplete documentation references, or point to inaccessible datasets. These practices lead to enormous difficulties in identifying the data that reliably underlies a paper and reusing them.

The technical solution (see <https://zenodo.org/communities/konsortswd-ta5-m1>) relies on ePic API (https://www.pidconsortium.net/?page_id=112) to handle PIDs on an element level. The service aims to improve data findability and accessibility at a more granular level of studies by assigning PIDs to fine-grained dataset elements like survey variables. PIDs for individual elements can be referenced and retrieved with the necessary metadata for both machine-actionable and human access. Four use cases for survey variables and qualitative data files in the Social Sciences are presented, addressing how partners adopt more fine-grained PIDs according to their needs, data types and available services. Each institution selected as a use case partner plays an essential role in the PID service evaluation, connecting their research data activities to the PID technical solution. The use cases also demonstrate how researchers can effortlessly find and cite data. Use case partners are the Higher Education Analytical Data System (HEADS) project from the German Center for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (DZHW), the GESIS Data Archive from the Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences (GESIS), including the GESIS harmonization tool QuestionLink, the German Socio-Economic Panel

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(SOEP-Core), a longitudinal study from the German Institute for Economic Research (DIW) and the Qualiservice qualitative data collection from the University of Bremen indented.

Our approach is to provide a registration service to assign PIDs to data elements below the study and dataset level to boost reliable method for overcoming data citation challenges. Referencing research data and their elements with PIDs supports FAIR data usage by using a disambiguate-proof as a unique identification. A single data point, the PID, enhances data citation, reuse, and direct access for both automated (i.e., by a computer program) and human access. PIDs for the individual data elements of a data set simplify FAIR data management, benefiting researchers and research data centres (RDCs) by promoting credible results and ensuring sustainable data reusability.

RDCs benefit from PIDs in data governance activities and the services they provide. Without unique identifiers, non-standard data practices create inefficiencies for data providers in identifying critical variables and for researchers reusing them. PIDs offer numerous advantages for machine-actionable features, such as enabling citation tracking and impact measurement, linking articles using the same dataset elements. It empowers the RDC's authority by demonstrating a commitment to best practices, enhancing its reputation in the research community by adopting recommendations to support PIDs at multiple granularity levels, such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) PID policy (see doi: 10.2777/926037). Researchers benefit from more precise variable identification, leading to accurate citation methods and increased trust in data due to its transparent provenance.

Researchers, data holders and data stewards, RDCs managers, data interoperability and informatics experts will learn the main advantages of assigning PIDs below study level because it improves the FAIRness of research data, enables transparent data citation, and favours reproducibility, facilitating data sharing and reuse.

Keywords:

Persistent Identifiers - PIDs. Research data citation. Research data services - technical infrastructure.

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